

Decentralized Wastewater Treatment in Arctic Climates: Lagoon limitations and MBR-HIX Innovations

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Abstract

This study assesses wastewater treatment lagoon efficiency in a northern Canadian community, focusing on physicochemical parameters, human enteric viruses, and PFAS micropollutants. An anoxic-aerobic MBR combined with a hybrid ion exchange (HIX) nanotechnology resin column was operated under simulated northern conditions to explore alternative solutions. Results showed that the MBR-HIX treatment effectively removed contaminants, while nanofiber membranes had better fouling resistance and less maintenance requirements than commercial PVDF membranes. This study revealed that the proposed MBR-HIX configuration has great potential for sustainable wastewater treatment in remote northern regions.

Keywords

Decentralized treatment; membrane bioreactor; northern communities; PFAS; wastewater treatment lagoons; water reuse

INTRODUCTION

Wastewater treatment lagoons are one of the most adopted methods for decentralized communities in the north. Nevertheless, substantial data regarding the efficiency of lagoon systems within those communities is lacking. As such, the primary objective of this study was to assess the performance of a wastewater treatment lagoon system in a northern Canadian community to identify its feasibility and evaluating the need for an alternative treatment method or improvements. This research involved the analysis of physicochemical parameters, the detection of human enteric viruses, and PFAS micropollutants in raw wastewater, wastewater treatment lagoons, and nearby natural wetlands, in order to evaluate environmental and public health risks (Boleydei et al., 2024).

As an alternative decentralized treatment, the use of a membrane bioreactor (MBR) combining physical separation with biological treatment is promising, not only for wastewater treatment but also for water reuse, as well as for nutrient recovery (Boleydei and Vaneeckhaute, 2024). As a second objective, an anoxic-aerobic MBR system was tested at 4° C using both a nanofiber membrane and a conventional PVDF membrane as a reference, aiming to minimize fouling and cleaning requirements. Finally, the MBR system was integrated with a hybrid ion exchange resin (HIX) impregnated with iron oxide nanoparticles to complete the treatment in terms of phosphorus and nitrate removal. The MBR-HIX system was operated for around 250 days at pilot scale to check upon the performance and reliability under extreme conditions. The pilot-scale setup operated in the lab simulated real-world constraints of northern regions and, therefore, proved useful for deducing experiences related to sustainable wastewater treatment solutions, balancing effectiveness with

practicality in remote settings bound by resource limitations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study site and sampling

This research was carried out among the Inuit community of Kangiqsualujjuaq (58° 17.99' N, 65° 41' 56.99" W) on the eastern shore of Ungava Bay at the mouth of the George River. The population living in this community was approximately 956 people equivalents in 2021 (Boleydei et al., 2024). Because of the long frost season, sampling was only possible during the summer. Therefore, fieldwork was carried out in July and August 2022 to have the best conditions for this sampling campaign. The studied community collects and transports wastewater by tanker trucks to the lagoons for treatment. The output of the lagoons is released into several inland water bodies (Boleydei et al., 2024). Samples of raw wastewater, wastewater treatment lagoons (cells A-B-C), and nearby natural wetlands were collected based on Standard Method for Examination of Water and Wastewater 1060- Collection and preservation of samples (Association, 1926).

Northern wastewater characterization and wastewater treatment lagoons' efficiency

Physicochemical parameters. Temperature, dissolved oxygen (DO), and pH of wastewater samples were measured in-situ using DO (Cole-Parmer) and pH (Fisher Scientific Accumet AB200) meters. Then, samples were transported on ice and analysed at Laval University following standard holding periods. Additional parameters, including electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), total solids (TS), and total suspended solids (TSS), were measured based on standard methods. Chemical oxygen demand (COD), ammonium (NH_4^+), total nitrogen (TN), and phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) were analysed using a HACH spectrophotometer with TNT test kits, and removal efficiencies were calculated (Bankole et al., 2017; Boleydei et al., 2024).

Detection of human enteric viruses. Frozen wastewater samples were thawed, pH-adjusted, and spiked with Murine Norovirus (MNV) as an internal control. After clarification via centrifugation and filtration, viruses were concentrated using 100 kDa centrifugal filters. Viral RNA and DNA were extracted using a QIAamp Viral RNA Mini Kit, and RT-qPCR (for RNA viruses) and qPCR (for DNA viruses) were performed in duplicate to detect target viruses (Boleydei et al., 2024).

PFAS detection. Sample extraction and analysis were performed by Eurofins Environment Testing using UPLC-MS/MS to quantify 40 PFAS components, following EPA Draft Method 1633 (USEPA, 2021) and SGS AXYS Method MLA-110 (Breitmeyer et al., 2023; Gewurtz et al., 2024). Quality control included laboratory control samples (LCS), duplicates, and calibration standards to ensure accuracy and reproducibility, with recoveries validated by spiked control samples (Schleederer et al., 2024).

MBR experiments

Experimental setup and operating conditions. As illustrated in Figure 1, a pre-anoxic aerobic membrane bioreactor was designed to treat real municipal wastewater from Université Laval's wastewater treatment plant. Various temperatures, mainly low temperatures, to simulate northern conditions and hydraulic retention times (HRTs) of 48 and 24 hours were applied to the system. Wastewater was continuously fed into the anoxic tank and then flew by gravity into the bioreactor tank. A peristaltic pump allowed recirculation between the two tanks. During the over 250-day experiment, two microfiltration flat-sheet membranes were tested: a commercial Synder PVDF membrane and a novel nanofiber membrane produced by Innobrane Team at Istanbul Technical University, Turkey. The permeate flow was controlled by a peristaltic pump, cycling on for 7

minutes, backwashing for 2 minutes, and off for 1 minute. Both membranes' removal efficiency, flux, and maintenance requirements were compared.

Figure 1. MBR-HIX configuration proposed in this study.

Ion exchange nanotechnology column integration. For better PO_4^{3-} removal, an ion exchange resin column impregnated with FerrIX A33E (iron oxide nanoparticles) was integrated just after the nanofiber membrane in the MBR setup. The nanofiber membrane effluent was flown upward through an 8-cm-high resin column packed with 15 g resin.

Analytical methods. The concentrations of COD, NH_4^+ , TN, NO_3^- , and PO_4^{3-} in the influent, anoxic tank, bioreactor tank, and membrane effluents were analysed using Hach standard test methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Northern wastewater characterization and wastewater treatment lagoons' efficiency

Physicochemical parameters. Wastewater lagoons exhibited removal efficiencies of 94% for TSS, 70% for TS, 99% for NH_4 , 61% for TN, 65% PO_4^{3-} , and 91% for COD. However, the lagoon system was not able to effectively reduce the TSS, COD, and PO_4^{3-} concentrations to acceptable levels, posing significant environmental and human health risks. Since the community heavily depends on land and water resources, this issue requires immediate attention to address the shortcomings and safeguard the environment and the community's well-being.

Human enteric viruses. The detection of Noroviruses GI and GII in raw wastewater, cell A and cell C samples suggests active circulation of these viruses within the community. Noroviruses are the leading cause of non-bacterial gastroenteritis globally (Bányai et al., 2018). In addition to noroviruses, rotavirus, adenovirus, and JCpYV were also identified in cell A, whereas no targeted enteric viruses were found in cell B. HuNoV GI and GII were consistently detected across all wetland samples at comparable levels. The presence of noroviruses in wetlands downstream of cell C highlights their persistence, suggesting that the human enteric viruses have the potential to contaminate the environment beyond the settling lagoons.

PFAS. Among 40 target PFAS, eight were detected in samples from raw wastewater, wastewater treatment lagoons, natural wetlands, and Ungava Bay. Total PFAS concentrations ranged between

45.9-56.1 ng/L in the wastewater treatment lagoons, 36.6-70.8 ng/L in the natural wetlands, and 7.3 ng/L in Ungava Bay. The most frequently detected PFAS were 6:2 FTS, PFHxA, and PFNA.

MBR-HIX integration

Removal efficiency. Table 1 presents the MBR-HIX performance results in treating municipal wastewater. This table specifically shows the results obtained at 4°C and a hydraulic retention time (HRT) of 48 hours. As the data shows, the MBR-HIX system demonstrates the ability to effectively remove contaminants even at low temperatures, showcasing its potential for applications in cold climates.

Table 1. MBR-HIX performance in real municipal wastewater treatment at a temperature of 4°C and an HRT of 48 hours.

Parameter	Removal efficiency (%)					Overall removal efficiency (%)
	Anoxic tank	Bioreactor tank	Commercial membrane	Nanofiber membrane	HIX resin column	
TSS	94	33	75	50	-	99
COD	85	41	42	48	71	98
NH ₄ ⁺	36	47	16	25	-	94
PO ₄ -P	20	25	10	13	100	100
NO ₃ -N	55	-25	16	28	44	77

Membranes' maintenance requirements. The nanofiber membrane was compared with the commercial membrane regarding maintenance requirements and cleaning efforts. The commercial membrane had higher fouling tendencies: it needed frequent cleaning with deionized water and occasional chemical cleaning using sodium hydroxide. In contrast, the nanofiber membrane had lower fouling rates, requiring less frequent cleaning with DI water alone and no chemical cleaning during the 250-day study. It indicates that the nanofiber membrane is more suitable for remote areas where technical expertise and resources are limited, while also being more environmentally sustainable due to reduced reliance on cleaning chemicals.

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